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SYNTHESIS AND ANTI-BACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 2-SUBSTITUTED-4,5-DIMETHYL IMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present study is to synthesize a series of 2-substituted-4,5-dimethyl imidazoles (IM1-IM6) by refluxing butan-2,3-dione with different substituted aldehydes in the presence of ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid. The synthesized compounds IM1-IM6 was screened for antimicrobial activity. Out of 6 imidazole compounds IM3, IM4, IM6 exhibited moderate inhibition against gram negative bacterial species and especially against *Escherichia coli* while IM3, IM6 and IM4 showed maximum activity against most gram negative organisms. Against gram positive organisms almost all compound of the series exhibited maximum inhibition, especially IM2 and IM3 showed highest inhibition against *B. megaterium*. We can conclude that some compounds were exhibiting competent biological activity against both gram negative & gram positive bacterial species. Thus imidazole derivatives are having the significant anti microbial activity.

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INTRODUCTION

The branch of chemistry dealing with synthesis, properties and application of heterocycles is heterocyclic chemistry. A heterocyclic compound is a cyclic compound that has hetero atoms in its cyclic ring. The imidazole (1,3-diaza-2,4-cyclopentadiene) is a planar, five membered heteroaromatic molecule with 3C and 2N atom in 1 and 3 positions. It is amphoteric in nature which is susceptible to both electrophilic and nucleophilic attack. It is highly stable to thermal, acid, base, oxidation and reduction conditions. It has extensive intramolecular hydrogen bonding. It exists in two equivalent tautomeric forms because the hydrogen atom can be located on either of the two nitrogen atoms. The compound is aromatic due to the presence of a sextet of π -electrons, consisting of a pair of electrons from the protonated nitrogen atom and one from each of the remaining four atoms of the ring. As an acid, the pKa of imidazole is 14.5, making it less acidic than carboxylic acids, phenols and imides, but slightly more acidic than alcohols. The acidic proton is located on N-1. As a base, the pKa of the conjugated acid (cited below as pKBH⁺ to avoid confusion between the two) is approximately 7, making imidazole approximately sixty times more basic than pyridine. These properties are explained by the resonance interactions, which increase the basicity of the 3-nitrogen atom. Some resonance structures of imidazole are shown in scheme 1.

Figure 1: Resonance structures of Imidazole.

Many biological molecules are composed of imidazole rings. It has become an important moiety of many pharmaceuticals. Imidazole is used as antifungal, antibacterial, antiprotozoal, antihypertensive and is important compound of caffeine, theophylline and theobromine which act as central nervous stimulants. The main objective of our study is to synthesize a series of 2-substituted-4,5-dimethyl imidazoles IM1-IM6 by refluxing butan-2,3-dione with different substituted aldehydes in the presence of ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid and evaluating for antibacterial activity. It was revealed that some synthesized derivatives were exhibiting competent biological activity against both gram negative & gram positive bacterial species. The present research was done to investigate the anti microbial activity for different derivates of imidazoles which are synthesized and their application in drug therapy. There is an increase in drug resistance and has become a challenge for the health care providers. Thus, in the present study we aim to synthesize a new chemical class of heterocyclic compounds to overcome the problem of microbial resistance. Imidazole derivatives are having high therapeutic properties which are useful for the researches to synthesize large number chemotherapeutic drugs comprising of imidazole nucleus. Thus the incorporation of imidazole nucleus has become an important strategy in drug discovery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure 2: Reactions conditions (a) Glacial acetic acid, stir, rt, 1-2h (yield 65-82%).

Table 1: Derivatives 2-substituted-4,5-dimethyl-1H-imidazoles.

SNO	R compound
IM1.	H
IM2.	C ₆ H ₅
IM3.	CH ₃
IM4.	4-H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₅
IM5.	2-O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₅
IM6.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅

One pot synthesis of 2-substituted-4,5-dimethyl imidazole derivatives involves the reaction between 2,3-butan-dione, ammonium acetate and aldehyde compounds at room temperature with vigorous stirring for 1-2hrs. The product formed gives 65-82% yield. Six aldehyde derivatives were used to synthesize six respective imidazole derivatives. The product formed was confirmed by TLC and the impurities were removed by performing column chromatography by using ethyl acetate and hexane as the solvents. The purified compound is tested for anti-microbial activity.

Antimicrobial activity of imidazole derivatives:

The test was performed by using the agar cup borer method, with some modifications using Streptomycin as reference for bacterial activity. A test tube containing sterile melted top agar (1.5 %) previously cooled at room temperature with 0.2 ml suspension of the test culture, mixed methodically and poured in the petri dish containing sterile base agar medium (autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min.) then allowed it to solidify. The cup borer was sterilized by dipping into absolute ethanol and flaming it then allowed to cool it. With the help of sterile cup-borer, three cups in the agar-plate were marked and were injected with 0.1 ml of test solution, 0.1 ml of standard solution and 0.1 ml of DMSO solvent respectively. Then the plates were allowed to diffuse for 20 min. in refrigerator at 4-5°C. The plates were then incubated in upright position at 37°C for 24 hrs. After incubation, the relative susceptibility of the micro-organisms to the potential antimicrobial agent is demonstrated by a clear zone of growth inhibition around the cup. The inhibition zone caused by the various compounds on the micro-organisms was measured and the activity was rated on the basis of the size of the inhibition zone.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesized compounds were screened 'in vitro' for antimicrobial activity. From the data presented in table1 &2, it is clear that out of 6 imidazole compounds IM3, IM4, IM6 exhibited moderate inhibition against gram negative bacterial species and especially against Escherichia coli while IM3, IM6 and IM4 showed maximum activity against most gram negative organisms. Against gram positive organisms almost all compound of the series exhibited maximum inhibition, especially IM2 and IM3 showed highest inhibition against B. megaterium.

Table 2: Anti microbial activity of imidazoles:

Compound code	Inhibition zone against (in mm)			
	E. coli	P. aeruginosa	B. subtilis	B. megaterium
IM1	16	13	25	27
IM2	14	12	27	28
IM3	20	17	28	30
IM4	19	16	20	23
IM5	14	12	20	20
IM6	20	14	21	25
Streptomycin	35	34	35	36

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have developed a facile protocol for the synthesis and optimization of a series of 2-substituted-4,5-dimethyl imidazole derivatives (IM1-IM6) under Sharpless conditions through click chemistry approach using glacial acetic acid as a catalyst at ambient temperature and evaluating them for antimicrobial activity. Comparison with the MIC values IM3, IM4, IM6 exhibited moderate inhibition against gram negative bacterial species and especially against Escherichia coli while IM3, IM6 and IM4 showed maximum activity against most gram negative organisms. Against gram positive organisms almost all compound of the series exhibited maximum inhibition, especially IM2 and IM3 showed highest inhibition against B. megaterium. Thus these imidazole derivatives were showing the significant antibacterial activity.

REFERENCES

1. Thomas L. Gilchrist. Heterocyclic Chemistry. 3rd ed. Addison Wesley: Essex. England. 1997; 414 pp. ISBN 0-582-27843-0.
2. Eicher, Theophil, Siegfried Hauptmann, and Andreas Speicher. The Chemistry of Heterocycles: Structure, Reactions, Syntheses, and Applications. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH. 2003; ISBN 3527307206
3. Joule J. A. and K. Mills. Heterocyclic Chemistry. 4th ed. Malden. MA: Blackwell Science. 2000; ISBN 0632054530
4. McMurry, John. Organic Chemistry. 6th ed. Belmont, CA: Brooks/Cole. 2004; ISBN 0534420052
5. Morrison, Robert T., and Robert N. Boyd. Organic Chemistry. 6th ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall. 1992; ISBN 0-13-643669-2
6. Solomons, Graham T W and Craig B. Fryhle. Organic Chemistry. 8th ed. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley. 2004; ISBN 0471417998
7. Abdallah M, Zaaferany I, Khairo K S and Sobhi M. Inhibition of carbon steel corrosion by Iron(III) and imidazole in sulfuric acid. Int. J. Electrochem. Sci. 2012; 7, 15641579.
8. Akkawi M, Aljazzar A., AbulHa M., and Abu-Remeleh Q. The effect of cis-2-(1Himidazole-2-yl)-1H-imidazole dichloro platinum (II) on the in-vitro formation of Hematin. British. J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. 2012; 3, 65-69.
9. Antonijevic, M. M., and Petrovic, M. B. (2008). Copper corrosion inhibitors. A review. Int. J. Electrochem. Sci. 3, 1-28.
10. Bellina, F., Cauteruccio, S., and Rossi, R. (2007). Synthesis and biological activity of vicinal diaryl-substituted 1H-imidazoles. Tetrahedron 63, 4571-4624.
11. Bereket, G., Hur, E., and Ogretir, C. (2002). Quantum chemical studies on some imidazole derivatives as corrosion inhibitors for iron in acidic medium. J. Mol. Struct. (Theochem) 578, 79-88.
12. Bhandari, K., Srinivas, N., Marrapu, V.K., Verma, A., Srivastava, S., and Gupta, S. (2010). Synthesis of substituted aryloxy alkyl and aryloxy aryl alkyl imidazoles as antileishmanial agents. Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett. 20, 291-293.
13. Bhatnagar, A., Sharma, P.K., and Kumar, N. A. (2011). Review on "Imidazoles": their chemistry and pharmacological potentials. Int. J. Pharm. Tech. Res. 3, 268-282.
14. Brown, E. G. (1998). Ring Nitrogen and Key Biomolecules; Kluwer Academic Press: U. K. (Chapter 2).
15. Chawla, A., Sharma, A., and Sharma, A. K. (2012). Review: A convenient approach for the synthesis of imidazole derivatives using microwaves. Der Pharma Chemica 4, 11.
16. Clark, B., Allway, P., Zuberi, T., Singer, S., Heckler, C., and Friedrich, L. (1858). Photographic element containing a speed-enhancing compound. WO2005/036262, 2005. Debus, H. (1858). Ueber die einwirkung des ammoniaks auf glyoxal Justus Liebigs Ann. der Chem. 107, 199-208.
17. Di Santo, R., Tafi, A., Costi, R., Botta, M., Artico, M., Corelli, F., Forte, M., Caporuscio, F., Angiolella, L., and Palamara, A.T. (2005). Antifungal Agents. 11. N-Substituted derivatives of 1-[(Aryl)(4-aryl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl)methyl]-1H-imidazole: Synthesis, anticandida activity, and QSAR studies. J. Med. Chem. 48, 5140-5153.

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